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Online Education and COVID-19 Pandemic: Challenges for Higher Education

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In the last two years, not only India but the entire world has witnessed the danger and consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, surely it has come as the biggest pandemic of the century that shook the entire human race from within. This pandemic has affected all of us, due to which we have to make changes in our lifestyle. In order to stop the disease from spreading, all higher educational institutions in India had to close as of March, 2020. Suddenly, we had to convert our entire educational system to an online format in order to both help the students and stop the pandemic from spreading. There was no better option than this to continue studies. India is a developing country and here the necessary infrastructure for online education, trained teachers, and policy for online education was in a development order. Therefore, there are now many issues facing students, teachers, management, parents, and policymakers as a result of the pandemic and the transition of the entire higher educational system towards online and ICT-based education. In this review-based article, the researcher has tried to explain the challenges faced by stakeholders especially in higher education during COVID-19.

“The challenges are there, but they are only temporary challenges. Online education will flourish...(Philip Regier). India is one of the biggest developing countries in the world and its diversity makes it distinct from other developing countries in the world. Most of the people in India still rely on agriculture for their livelihood. They use mobile phones for communication but are still away from smartphones and are not exposed to internet access (Prasad, 2021). Hence for effective incorporation of online education, it is very essential to develop pre-requisite infrastructure and internet facilities across the country. But this biggest hurdle on the way is that in India more than 65% population still lives in rural or remote areas so it is a difficult task for the

government to develop the essential infrastructure which is required for online education in less time. It will surely take more time to develop basic infrastructure and resources in rural and remote areas of India. Along with the good quality of internet accessibility of smartphones and laptops is also a big question mark for the government (Atika, et. al., 2020). Because those families who belong to the Economically Weaker Section and Marginalized groups cannot afford smartphones, laptops, and a good internet connection for their children. But in the difficult time of the pandemic, no other better way of teaching and learning is available so we all rely on online education. In India, from March, 2020 all educational institutes remain closed. Our country's higher education system abruptly moved toward online and ICT-based teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Numerous problems and difficulties are presented to India's higher education system as a result of this abrupt change in the teaching environment.

Because classroom pedagogies were an essential intervening variable in face-to-face instruction, many different elements have an impact on teachers and students when using an online or ICT-based teaching method or applying an e-learning pedagogy. And the interaction between students and teachers is limited from one screen to another screen therefore use of non-verbal communication and classroom pedagogies are limited to a certain level (Raashid, et. al., 2020). Sometimes in offline classrooms, teachers use different kinds of pedagogies for the needs of different types of students so that they can reach each and every student. And every student learns from college/institute but in the current scenario of online education, it is difficult for teachers to use a variety of pedagogy in one class as per the need for an inclusive classroom.

Review of Related Literature

Mishra, S. (2009). had worked on e-learning; in their work, he gave an overview of e-learning in India

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and explained that the ministry of human resource development and the union grants commission were working together to develop a national program to support online and ICT-based teaching and learning across the nation. Based on research experience, researchers feel that the establishment of statutory bodies for Online Education in India is very important for the upcoming time. Verma, A. (2020) has studied how medical undergraduate students perceive online teaching during COVID-19. In her work she explains medical education is also affected due to pandemic, further, she explains after teaching for more than one month through online mode she found 47% of students want online teaching must be a part of the curriculum. In her research, she addresses some issues related to a lack of training in using ICT devices. Perryman (2013). Explicitly explained in his work in India we have a huge requirement for skilled teachers. Existing teachers are not trained for online mode; they need immediate pre-service training programs so that they can improve the standard of the Indian higher education system further. He described how open educational resources (OER) are used in India and how they can be useful for both teachers and students while conducting online and ICT-based instruction. Muthu, et, al., (2021) worked on Indian students' opinions and preferences on online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic For their research project, they polled agricultural students on how they would adjust to online learning. Researchers in this study indicated that there are still many unanswered questions regarding the applicability and usability of e-learning in India. In his study, he concluded more than 70% of students were ready to adopt online teaching and mostly preferred smartphones for this. Atika Qazi (2020) during the COVID-19 pandemic, worked on converting traditional to online education. Do developed and developing countries cope similarly? In his research, he conducted a cross-sectional study of 320 students to determine the level of SATISFACTION WITH ONLINE EDUCATION DURING THE Covid-19 outbreak. Students in urban regions are more satisfied (about 50%) with online-based learning than students in rural areas, according to the findings of this study (around 37%). Dhawan, S. (2020). Did work on online learning during COVID-19 in her descriptive analysis she discussed the Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities,

and Challenges (SWOC) examination of online education. Palvia, et. al, (2018) conducted a study on Online Education: Worldwide Status, Challenges, Trends, and Implications in which they explained that by 2025, online education would become a mainstream method of delivering education, but that the quality and quantity of online education would be a crucial factor that we would need to take into account. Rasheed, A. et, al, (2020) worked on online learning and challenges in this research work in blended mode with face-to-face teaching and online learning which kinds of problems arise in front of teachers and college/institute management? Basically for teachers use of technology related to online teaching is a real concern but providing training for them for such type of blended learning is also a big challenge for college/institute management and other authorities. Diane, Hockridge. (2013) did a study titled Distance Education: Challenges for Educators Using Online and Distance Education to Prepare Students for Relational Professions. In his research work, he explained issues and challenges for teacher educators in implementing online and distance education. For this study researcher selected theology educators from an Australian theological institute and the findings of this research study provide a platform for educators to development of formational learning. Objectives of the Study are:

- To understand the preparedness, designing, and effectiveness of online education in the context of higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic.
- To describe concerns and obstacles that the coronavirus has posed for higher education during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Methodology

This study is descriptive, attempting to comprehend concerns and challenges for higher education in India in adapting online education during times of crisis and pandemic, such as COVID-19. The analysis was carried out to better understand the different concerns and obstacles linked with online education for higher education. A content analysis was utilized to analyze the data acquired from various sources for the study, and researchers employed a descriptive method for this analysis. Researchers also considered the qualitative component of the research study. This research study

was fully based on secondary data and an analytical review was done for data collection.

Challenges for Higher Education System

Changes in the higher education system were anticipated a few years ago but a sudden complete move towards online education was not anticipated. That makes teaching and learning more challenging for teachers as well as students because we are not ready for this spontaneity in Education (Verma, et, al., 2020). The management of the higher institutes faces a significant problem in making the full transition from offline, face-to-face mode to online mode. Because our curriculum followed in higher education in India was not designed for a completely online mode. And curricular and co-curricular activities were remains an integral part of our higher education curriculum. During this pandemic, our teachers and educators start thinking about alternatives to those co-curricular activities through virtual mode, but there is no rigorous research work available that the virtual activities will be helpful for an inclusive online classroom where learners of different needs present there (Dhawan, 2020). Therefore, a few questions also cross the researcher's thoughts. It would be beneficial to explore these problems and difficulties from the perspectives of students, teachers, parents, administrators, and policymakers.

Issues and Challenges for Students and Parents

Before the pandemic, students are habitual to limited use of ICT in the process of teaching and learning but a sudden complete shift of education towards online/ICT may bring a few challenges in front of students as well as parents:

- Those students who are good in the live interactive face-to-face mode of teaching and learning feel monotonous in online teaching and learning because maximum communication is limited from one screen to another screen.
- Students and parents are not confident about the assessment process because there are no pre-existing guidelines, documents, or policies available for online assessment.
- Since all students are not tech savvy, sometimes they feel difficulty in adjusting to online teaching and learning.

- Those students who are very tech savvy in such types of teaching do not pose in front of them new challenges to learning so they do not use their full capacity in this.
- Nationwide connectivity and speed of internet, not even so students from rural and remote areas suffer problems in connection with online classes and we have a few examples in which students from these areas walk miles away from their home in search of suitable internet connection.
- Students belonging to economically weaker sections and marginalized groups cannot afford equipment and devices which are essential for online teaching and learning.
- Sometimes education based on ICT is more costly and monotonous in comparison to the face-to-face mode of teaching in which students have enough time for collaboration, work in groups, discussion in face-to-face mode, learning through hands-on activities and the environment works as a catalyst for learning.
- Online teaching and learning may affect the health of students negatively because such types of learning provide limited scope for the engagement of psychomotor skills and physical skills.

Issues and Challenges for Teachers

- Teachers who are not well equipped with online teaching and learning feel difficulty engaging students through online mode because sudden lockdowns in the country don't provide them enough time to train themselves (Martin, 2020).
- Since offline teaching strategies are an integral part of teaching and learning so it is difficult for teachers in online teaching and learning to implement a few aspects of offline teaching strategies like nonverbal communication, gesture-posture, and use of voice pitch.
- Sometimes online class is more time-consuming than the face-to-face mode of education so it may put an extra workload on teachers.
- This is very important to develop faith and belief in online teaching among students and parents.
- Try to include students of different needs and individual differences in their online classroom.
- Since the need for online classrooms in comparison

to the face-to-face mode of teaching is completely different, so to catering, is also a challenge.

- Try to use online software like Google classroom, Mentimeter, Poll everywhere, etc. for online assessment of students.

Challenges for Management

- The big issue in front of higher institutes' management during the time of the pandemic is how they implement their curriculum in online mode. And when they don't have any official or authorized documents that can build trust among students and teachers.
- To provide online teaching and learning material to our students so that the learning can go on uninterrupted and also assess the learner's achievement with transparency.
- To prepare a pool of teachers in a short period of time who can take online classes and can implement ICT-based teaching and learning efficiently.
- To provide seamless internet connectivity to the college/institute staff so that they can update all online reports of students timely and ensure all teachers can deliver their lectures on time to students.
- Publish the result of the online assessment timely and with full transparency so that students can participate in the assessment process with full enthusiasm.

Challenges for Policy Makers

- During the time of pandemic there is no special curriculum available for students which are specially designed for online education. So, there is an urgent need for such types of documents, curriculum, or policy which is specially focused on online education.
- Policymaking for large groups is a time-consuming task because it requires a lot of expertise, studies, the grass root level of research, areas of priority increase with time, and also experience in specific field needs is a must. In this time of the pandemic, there is really less time to interact with such types of target groups who can actually suffer problems in online education so it is quite challenging for the government to prepare policy in this small span of time.

- Sometimes implementation of policy takes time because geographically India is a large country and there are state wise many languages and cultures followed by a group of people therefore preparing a single policy for the whole nation and translating it to different regional languages will take time. And preparing modules for heads, principals, and college/institute teachers and providing them formal training from the district level to the block level is a time-consuming task for the government and policymakers also.
- To make sure whatever document they prepare must be flexible and give autonomy to students so that they can build their understanding through reflecting over text and discussion.

Suggestions

- From the researchers' point of view there is an urgent need for official documents or policies for online teaching and learning and also for the assessment of the same.
- Central government and state government in collaboration with different universities and institutes must initiate a few awareness programs about online teaching and also for assessment so trust can build up among students and teachers.
- Since most of the working staff in higher institutes are not much familiar with the equipment and use of online education so there is a need for formal training by college/institute management and state government so they can adopt such type of technology easily.
- During the COVID-19 pandemic many good institutions in India conducted Open Book Exams for semester assessment and evaluation of students but from the side of teachers and students, a lot of problems arose. So, in this regard clear and structured guidelines for examination and submission should be prepared and provide proper time for answer scripts submissions of the students. If any students fail to upload their answer scripts due to various reasons then alternative options should be designed for the submission of the same.
- We see in the past few months assessment and evaluation of answer scripts of the open book exam is not an easy task for universities and Institutes.

Because for timely assessment and evaluation, they need well-equipped and trained evaluators in large numbers so from the researcher's point of view, they can prepare a pool of trained and skilled evaluators in advance according to various subjects to complete the work on time.

- Periodically e-assessment should be part of online education and provide online remedial teaching to weak students or those students who need this.
- At this critical time of the COVID-19 pandemic principals or heads of colleges/institutes tried to conduct online parent and teachers' meetings wherein parents can share their doubts, and worries about their child and online education with their teachers. So, such types of meetings will become a good bridge between parents and teachers.
- This is important for students in online or open-book exams; they must write their genuine and original thoughts based on their understanding. So, in this sequence, it is important for college/institute management they should use software like plagiarism checkers, etc. to avoid repetitive thoughts and answers during students' assessments and evaluations.
- In today's scenario a lot of online software is available for periodic assessment of students, but college/institute management tries to use such types of software which are user-friendly and keep informed of students confidential.
- Heads and principals must establish good relationships with teachers, staff, students, and parents and arrange periodic meetings with all college/institute families to transmit the love of learning among all.

Conclusions

In the past two years, we are all going through a hard time due to the COVID-19 pandemic and it affects the higher education system not only in India but also across the world. Providing constant and uninterrupted learning for students was the motto of the government in India. So, for constant teaching and learning during the pandemic, we are using online education because at this time no better alternative for education is available for us. During this pandemic, we used online teaching as an

opportunity but this sudden shift in education brings some challenges to higher education (Saxena, 2020, Realey, 2020). This pandemic creates new learning opportunities for students and teachers at their homes but at the same time, they feel some issues and challenges which are obvious in this sudden change in higher education.

Since in absence of uniform policy or documents regarding online education in India some students and parents are quite uncertain about the assessment and evaluation process so there is an urgent need for the same. There is a need for properly structured and Planned Open Book examinations but at the same time, they must be flexible so that students from all socio-economic statuses can easily participate in such types of exams. In this pandemic, a lot of students feel discomfort and uneasy with online education so college/institute heads and principals should take initiative for that and arrange periodic meetings with students and teachers that boost some confidence and positivity inside students about online education.

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